

NUMERICAL MODELING OF DELAMINATION DURING MACHINING OF LFRP COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Long Fiber Reinforced Polymer (LFRP) composites, are widely used in different industrial sectors due to their excellent mechanical properties and lightness.

LFRP composites are the general terminology to represent three main families of composites based on glass, carbon and aramid fibers (mainly Kevlar) in a polymeric matrix (commonly denoted GFRP, CFRP and AFRP/KFRP respectively). Long fibers can be unidirectional or multidirectional (woven). Due to his competitive cost, Glass fiber reinforced plastics (GFRP) are the most commonly used. Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) and aramid fiber (commonly Kevlar) reinforced plastics (AFRP) present better specific strength, higher specific stiffness and lighter weight. CFRP composites are widely used in structural components in aircrafts. AFRPs replace CFRPs when higher strength, lightness and toughness are required, for instance for personal protections [1].

The use of these materials in different mobile systems in aerospace and naval applications justifies the interest of understanding their behavior under dynamic loading. The possibility of suffering an impact of a foreign object is elevated in such applications. On the other hand, LFRP composites are also subjected to dynamic loading during the last stages of the component manufacture. Although the components are manufactured close to the final shape, they commonly require some machining

operations, mainly milling and drilling, previously to the final assembly, in order to achieve dimensional specifications [2]. Machining can be considered a dynamic process involving high cutting speed, and extreme contact conditions at the interface tool-chip [3]. Both impact and machining process can induce irreversible damage in LFRP composites. Among the different damage mechanisms, delamination is the main responsible of damage extension and loss in residual properties.

Most works dealing with orthogonal cutting of composite materials, are based on two dimensional numerical models and assume the hypothesis of plane stress [4,5]. However the onset and progression of delamination damage are dependent on the matrix behavior when laminate is subjected to out-of-plane tensile and shearing stresses. Therefore two-dimensional analysis is not suitable for predicting delamination. On the other hand, only unidirectional laminate can be modeled, while quasi-isotropic laminates are used in structural applications due to their higher performance.

The implementation of 3D numerical models to predict out-of-plane damage induced on LFRP composite laminates after machining operations can lead to a better understand of the failure mechanisms and delamination onset [5].

In this paper, a 3D numerical model of composite machining considering out-of-plane damage is presented and validated with experimental results obtained from literature.

2 Damage modeling

Damage modeling is an important aspect for the accurate simulation of impact tests and machining processes of LFRP composites. Among the different techniques available to predict composite damage, the failure-criteria approach has demonstrated its accuracy in both static and dynamic loading states. Different failure criteria are proposed in the literature [6].

The analysis of the different models available for long fiber composites and the identification of damage model parameters, have motivated an international exercise developed between 1998 and 2004 [7] comparing different failure criteria under static conditions. No comparable study has been performed under dynamic loading. The most common failure criteria used in the dynamic conditions can be categorized in ply criteria which use an equation to predict the global failure of each ply, and complex criteria involving several failure modes (matrix cracking, matrix crushing, fiber failure, delamination, etc).

Although the complex failure of composite materials needs to distinguish between different failure modes, simple criteria have been used in several works to model the impact behavior [8,9] and the machining processes of composite materials [10].

The failure of composite materials cannot be predicted using Von Mises yield criterion that apply only to isotropic materials. The failure of anisotropic materials has been determined for many years by means of Hill criterion, which is an extension of Von Mises criterion to anisotropic materials. Tsai-Hill criterion is based on the application of the strength parameters present in Hill criterion to the critical strength values in three orthogonal directions formulating a criterion for LFRP composite, see Eq. 1 (X_1 and X_2 are the longitudinal and transversal strength respectively and S is the shear strength).

$$\frac{\sigma_1^2}{X_1^2} - \frac{\sigma_1 \sigma_2}{X_1^2} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{X_2^2} + \frac{\sigma_{12}^2}{S^2} \geq 1 \quad (1)$$

Tsai-Wu criterion [11] is a modification of Tsai-Hill criterion taking into consideration different values for tensile and compressive strength. The formulation of Tsai-Wu criterion is the same given in Eq. 1, but the values of the longitudinal and

transversal strengths are dependent on the tensile or compressive stress state.

These models do not allow predicting the different failure modes characterizing composite materials: fiber failure, matrix failure, and fiber-matrix interface. This limitation has motivated the formulation of more realistic failure criteria. The most common sets of criteria used in the analysis of composite material in dynamic conditions are those due to Hashin [12] and Hou [13], constituting a three-dimensional version of Chang-Chang criteria [14].

Both Hashin and Hou criterion consider different failure mechanism and equations. Four failure modes (fiber failure, matrix cracking, matrix crushing and delamination) are accounted in Hou criteria, considering quadratic interaction between stresses, see Table 1. Hashin formulation considers also four failure modes: tensile and compression failure of fiber and matrix, however delamination is not considered. A quadratic interaction between the components of the stress vector associated with the failure plane governs each mode.

3 Numerical model

A 3D numerical model of orthogonal cutting of LFRP was developed in ABAQUS/Explicit code. Dynamic explicit analysis was carried out using C3D8R, with 8-node brick elements with reduced integration available in ABAQUS/Explicit [15]. A scheme of the numerical model is presented in Fig.1.

Material behavior was modeled with a VUMAT subroutine, including failure criteria, a degradation procedure and an element deletion criterion. The failure criteria used in based on 3D Hashin criteria formulation. Since Hashin criteria does not consider delamination criterion, Hou formulation [13] was used to complete failure criteria. When a failure criterion is verified mechanical properties are degraded according to failure mode. Fiber failure implies that all the mechanical properties are degraded while matrix failure implies that only transverse mechanical are degraded. Delamination implies degradation of the out-of-plane mechanical properties. A procedure to remove the distorted elements, based on the maximum strain criterion was also implemented in the subroutine.

Table 1. Hou and Hashin criteria formulations.

Failure mode	Hashin Formulation	Hou formulation
Fiber tension	$d_{ft}^2 = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2}{S_L^2}\right)$	$d_f^2 = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2}{S_L^2}\right)$
Fiber compression	$d_{fc}^2 = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_c}\right)$	
Matrix cracking	$d_{mt}^2 = \left(\frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{Y_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2}{S_L^2}\right) + \left(\frac{\sigma_{23}^2 - \sigma_{22}\sigma_{33}}{S_T^2}\right)^2$	$d_{mt}^2 = \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_L}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{23}}{S_T}\right)^2$
Matrix crushing	$d_{mc}^2 = \frac{1}{Y_c} \left[\left(\frac{Y_c}{2S_T}\right)^2 - 1 \right] (\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) + \left(\frac{\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}}{2S_T}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{23}^2 + \sigma_{22}\sigma_{33}}{S_T^2}\right) + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2}{S_L^2}\right)$	$d_{mc}^2 = \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{-\sigma_{22}}{S_T}\right)^2 + \frac{Y_c \sigma_{22}}{4S_T^2 Y_c} - \frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y_c} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_L}\right)^2$
Delamination		$d_{del}^2 = \left(\frac{\sigma_{33}}{Z_T}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{23}}{S_T}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{31}}{S_L}\right)^2$

Parameters in table 1 are the following: σ_{11} , σ_{22} , and σ_{33} , are normal stresses in longitudinal, transverse and through-the-thickness direction respectively; σ_{12} , σ_{23} , and σ_{31} , are the shear stresses; X_T and X_C are the tensile and compressive strengths in longitudinal direction; Y_T and Y_C are the tensile and compressive strengths in the transverse direction; Z_T is the tensile strength in the through-the-thickness direction; S_L is the longitudinal shear strength; S_T is the transverse shear strength, (failure occurs when d_{ij} reaches the value 1).

The tool was assumed to be a rigid solid. The contact interaction at the tool-workpiece interface was modeled by using the algorithm surface–node surface contact available in ABAQUS/Explicit with a constant value of the friction coefficient equal to 0.5.

Mechanical properties, geometry and boundary conditions of the numerical model are presented in Fig. 1. Cutting parameters and tool and workpiece characteristics (depth of cut, cutting speed, rake angle, clearance angle, edge radius, laminate architecture) were coherently defined with the experimental work presented in [11,12] used for validation. A cutting length of 1 mm was assumed to ensure the stabilization.

Fig.1. Scheme of 3D FE model for orthogonal cutting of LFRP composite and associated mesh.

4 Results and discussion

In this section 3D model is applied to the analysis of orthogonal cutting of unidirectional and quasi-isotropic laminates. In the design of composite structures, stacking sequence has to be carefully selected in order to optimize the material response to service loads, thus unidirectional laminates are rarely used in industry.

Cutting force, intralaminar damage and delamination are obtained from the simulations. The study focused on a carbon FRP. The mechanical properties of the material are presented in Table 2. The analysis was performed for fiber orientation equal to 45° (for the unidirectional laminate) and also for the quasi-isotropic stacking sequence [45/-45/0/90]_s. The laminate thickness in the presented work was varied from 0.1 to 0.8 mm. The sensitivity of the mesh was analyzed carrying out successive discretizations, the final element size used in the workpiece was around $7\mu\text{m}$.

Table 2. Material properties.

Carbon epoxy T300/914	
Longitudinal modulus, E_1 (GPa)	136.6
Transverse modulus, E_2 (GPa)	9.6
In-plane shear modulus, G_{12} (GPa)	5.2
Major Poisson's ratio, ν_{12}	0.29
Through thickness Poisson's ratio, ν_{23}	0.4
Longitudinal tensile strength, X_T (MPa)	1500
Longitudinal compressive strength, X_c (MPa)	900
Transverse tensile strength, Y_T (MPa)	27
Transverse compressive strength, Y_c (MPa)	200
In-plane shear strength, S_{12} (MPa)	80
Longitudinal tensile strength, Z_T (MPa)	27
Longitudinal shear strength, S_L (MPa)	80
Transverse shear strength, S_T (MPa)	60

The complete chip formation for unidirectional laminates is analyzed in Fig 2 in terms of cutting force evolution and matrix crushing damage extension. At the beginning of the process, damage is concentrated around the tool tip. Later, it propagates through the primary shear zone reaching the free surface of the chip. The force value increases quickly during this first step. During the second phase the damage propagates and it is possible to observe a drop of the force corresponding with the formation of failure surface. Finally, complete chip is formed and a significant drop of the forces is observed.

Fig.2. Force and matrix crushing damage evolutions for a 0.8 mm quasi-isotropic CFRP.

The cutting force is represented in the Fig.3 for three different laminate thicknesses (0.1 mm, 0.4 mm and 0.8 mm). Similar results are obtained in terms of cutting force, however damage extension changes for different laminate thickness [5].

The main interest with the 3D numerical approach is the possibility to apply the model to quasi-isotropic laminates and the prediction of out-of-plane damage including delamination (corresponding with Hou criterion in the model presented in the present work).

Fig. 4 presents both delamination and matrix damage for quasi-isotropic laminate with stacking sequence [45/-45/0/90]_s. The penetration of the matrix damage in depth beneath the tool tip is significant. Moreover, it is observed a large extension of delamination area ahead of the tool (between the plies at 45° and -45°).

Initiation and progression of delamination damage are mainly dependent on the matrix behavior when out-of-plane tensile stresses appeared. On the other hand, the matrix cracking and crushing modes being the dominant damage mechanisms in the laminate plane are also influenced by the out-of-plane stresses. Thus 3D models are needed to predict machining induced damage on quasi-isotropic laminates.

Fig.3. Cutting forces for 45° unidirectional CFRP. Comparison between numerical predictions and experimental results [16]

Fig.4. Matrix failure and delamination damage observed during cutting for a [45/-45/0/90]_s CFRP

5 Conclusions

In this study a 3D model of orthogonal cutting is presented and applied to CFRP materials. It has been highlighted the necessity of 3D models to simulate cutting process of quasi-isotropic laminates. Moreover, it has been shown that the delamination damage is a critical phenomenon which should be simulated.

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7 References

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